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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Project progress.....	2
2.1 General achievements	2
2.2 Unforeseen issues.....	6
2.2.1 CMCC.....	6
2.2.2 CSA	6
2.2.3 UniZd	6
2.2.4 MMPI.....	6
2.2.5 AdSP	6
3. Conclusions	7

1. Executive Summary

This report documents the GUTTA project financial progress during the reporting period ranging from 2020-07-01 to 2021-06-30, corresponding to RP4 and RP5 altogether. Please note that full reporting information is declared on SIU and the present report just represents an overview of its key contents. Moreover, the report does not consider possible modifications to the present conditions, which may rise during the work of the FLCs.

When not re-defined here, shortcuts refer to the public GUTTA Glossary, which is found at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>

2. Project progress

The report is organized into General achievements (Sect. 2.1), and Unforeseen Issues (Sect. 2.2).

2.1 General achievements

Expenditures for RP4 were reported in SIU by LP-CMCC, PP2-CSA, PP3-UniZd, and PP4-MMPI. In RP5, also PP5-AdSP started reporting some costs. Notwithstanding the COVID-19 situation, but also thanks to the major amendment of the project, expenditures are generally occurring in a regular manner till RP5.

The overall financial progress, both at WP, activities and budget line levels, is summarized in Fig.1-6 for RP4 and RP5, defined as:

- RP4: 4th reporting period (2020-07-01 to 2020-12-31)
- RP5: 5th reporting period (2021-01-01 to 2021-06-30)

With respect to previous reports of this kind, we have updated the definitions of the fractions as follows:

- Done: cumulative absorption since project start, divided by planned cumulative absorption;
- Gap: difference between to-be-spent and actually-spent budget in given RP, divided by planned cumulative absorption. Negative values mean overspending;
- Remainder: complement to 1 of the sum of done and gap

Figure 1: Financial implementation status of GUTTA WPs during RP4. Blue is the absorbed fraction of the budget, cumulative of the first three RPs; orange is the cumulative missing fraction within the current RP, and grey is the remaining fraction until the end of the project.

Figure 2: as Fig.1 but for RP5.

Figure 3: Financial implementation status of GUTTA activities during RP4

Figure 4: As Fig.3 but for RP5.

Figure 5: Breakdown of financial implementation status of GUTTA through budget lines during RP4.

Figure 6: As in Fig.5, but for RP5.

The WP-breakdown (Fig.1-2) highlights that an absorption gap in WP3 could be recovered during RP5. The gap for WP4 is also about to be closed.

The overall implementation rate, defined as the actual cumulative absorption compared to the planned absorption, is 74.1%.

For the activities (Fig.3-4), an underspending is noticed just for A.4.3 “Maritime mobility data and COVID-19 pandemic dynamics”, which was renamed and modified with the major amendment. The underspending is due to the postponement of the external contract of PP4-MMPI, which will be finalized at the beginning of 2022, and by the no costs reporting in this activity by PP5-AdSP.

For the budget lines (Fig.5-6), the underspending noticed just for “External Expertise” is justified by the postponement mentioned above for PP4-MMPI.

2.2 Unforeseen issues

2.2.1 CMCC

- No issues

2.2.2 CSA

- Minor budget amendments were requested and are included in this RP documentation.

2.2.3 UniZd

- No issues

2.2.4 MMPI

- No issues

2.2.5 AdSP

- Starting reporting costs only in RP5.

3. Conclusions

The overall assessment of financial progress in RP4 and RP5 is positive. Thanks to continuing implementation and absorption by most partners, and the start of cost reporting also by PP4 and PP5, the GUTTA project is now again on the right financial trajectory.

The major amendment submitted and approved during RP5 is already producing beneficial effects with respect to the technical activities and related absorption plan.